

The Transformation of Punjabi Television: Milestones and Achievements

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Abstract

Despite concerns about the role of television in a developing democracy, television has emerged as a major vehicle for socio-economic change in India. If we look back to the past few decades, the electronic media is living in a golden age and is growing day by day. In this research paper, an attempt has been made to look at the early stage of Punjabi television. Which shows when and how the advent of Punjabi television and dominance of private channels started.

Keywords Transformation, Punjabi Television, Milestones, Achievements, Democracy.

Introduction

The development of electronic media is a part of the revolution which has brought great changes in the socio-economic condition of India. Despite concerns about the role of television in a developing democracy, television has emerged as a major vehicle for socio-economic change in India. If we look at the past few decades, electronic media is living in a golden age and is growing day by day, currently electronic media is on the cusp of success. It has contributed immensely to the Indian society. The development of electronic media has brought drastic changes in the socio-economic condition of India. Television has emerged as a major tool in India's social and economic transformation. The advent of television in India was carried out on 15 September 1959 as an experiment in a simple studio with a small transmitter. This experiment was made possible only by the equipment given by the US, a grant of 20,000 dollars from UNESCO and the experiment of Philips. The range of its transmitter was only 40 km. (Kumar, 2000) The second television station in India was started in 1972 in Mumbai. This was followed by expansion of television stations in Sri Nagar, Amritsar, Calcutta, Chennai and Lucknow. (Kumar, 2000)

Objective of study

Trying to find out the advent of Punjabi television channels and How did the development happen.

Review of Literature

In the year 1976, Doordarshan was separated from All India and made an independent institution and this year only Doordarshan started showing advertisements which was the main source of Doordarshan's income. In 1982, Doordarshan launched 'satellite broadcasting' through Inset 2A, the first Indian satellite. In 1982, white call TV. Color TV from The step up to has been completed. This was done keeping in mind the Asian Games to be held in Delhi. Doordarshan expanded rapidly in 1984 and installed a transmitter almost every day (*About | Prasar Bharati, n.d.*).

Main Text

Importance of research work: This research has tried to find out what was the status of Punjabi television at that time when private channels started to come in India and which

channels related to Punjabi language made a splash in the Indian media.

Journey of Punjabi Electronic Media from 1990 to 1999-

Pakistan established the first private free-to-air channel by the end of 1989. Which also reached 10 major cities of India. By the end of the 1990s, Shalimar and PTV. Both the Pakistani channels were watched with great interest in the neighboring states of Punjab, Rajasthan, Himachal Pradesh as well as in Delhi. These channels used to show a lot of Urdu drama and about their culture. (Thomas, 2005) Although at that time Doordarshan in India had spread its feet in almost more than half of India, but still people's attention was being drawn towards Pakistani dramas.

DD is the first among the Punjabi channels. Punjabi knocked which is DD. 1 was started on 29 September 1973 from Amritsar as a regional channel. After this, on 13 April 1979, this channel was established in Jalandhar. This channel started functioning fully from 1st June 1981. D.D. Punjabi was launched on 06 August 1998 and within 2 years, the channel became a 24 hour channel. D.D. Punjabi is also available in India and other countries where INSAT 3A and INSAT 4B satellites are available. D.D. Punjabi and 99.16 percent Punjabi, 0.79 percent Hindi, 0.05 percent Urdu programs are shown and reach 100 percent area of Punjab. (Prasar Bharti, 2016)

On 1 November 1966, the present state of Punjab came into existence. This day is celebrated as Punjab state day. Keeping this in mind, 'Punjabi World' channel was launched on 1 November 1998, which was a religious as well as entertainment channel. The tag line of this channel was 'Your Own Channel'. Punjabi World Channel Chairman Kishore Motni, Managing Director M. Sunil and Managing Director Rabinder Narayan. (Chatterjee, 1998)

'Punjabi World' channel was launched through private satellite 24 Thycom-3. In those times, the 'Punjabi World' channel' aimed to reach around 200 million Punjabi speaking people all over the world. (Punjabi Language Service Launched, 1998)

This channel had acquired the special rights of broadcasting directly from Shri Harminder Sahib Amritsar. Gurbani from Harmandir Sahib was broadcast live from November 1. (Singh, 2000) At the same time, this channel signed a written contract with Anandpur Sahib Foundation in which 'Punjabi World Channel' will be the official channel of Anandpur Sahib Foundation and Anandpur Sahib Foundation. The 300th anniversary being celebrated in the Sahib will be broadcast live. (Datta, 1998)

Presently Mr. Rabinder Narayan, Managing Director and President of PTC Network, launched the first Punjabi satellite channel, Punjabi World. Narayan is known for his unique achievement of putting Gurbani on the television map of the world. The team led by him started broadcasting Gurbani Kirtan from Sri Darbar Sahib, Amritsar in 1998. This channel shut down within a year. Because on the other hand 'Reminiscent India Television' was knocked out by 'Lashkara' Punjabi channel. whose programs had attracted the attention of the audience.

On 14 April 1999, two regional language channels were launched by 'Reminiscent India Television' (RITV) to cater to audiences in Asia. 'Gurjari' was in Gujarati language and 'Lashkara' was in Punjabi language. (Srivastav, 2005)

'Reminiscent India Television Limited' was incorporated on November 24, 1998 as an unlisted public company and is based in Maharashtra. It is classified as a public limited company. This company has three directors - Sunil Sethumadhawa Mukilmarthur, Abdul Sajid Shaikh and Subhash Minan. (Reminiscent India Television, 2020)

To keep the Punjabi and Gujarati people of India connected with their culture, customs and beliefs, Lashkara and Gurjari channels offered programs in a very sophisticated manner. In India, 'Lashkara' channel is considered to be the most successful regional language channel. The audience of this channel was not only in Punjab or Delhi, but its audience was very large in the entire northern region and wherever Punjabi lived in India, this channel was very popular. In addition, the channel claimed to have a wide and diverse range of religious, drama and comedy programs for all age groups.

'Lashkara Punjabi' was an entertainment channel that aired in analogue mode. In fact for the first time 'Lashkar' was telecast in digital mode only. The organizers said that it was working as a hindrance as cable TV in India. The operator had to pay for the digital license. (" RITV Chalks Up Success, 1999)

Meanwhile, 'Lashkara' was attracting advertisers. Because its audience was increasing day by day. In fact, with the end of 'Punjabi World', it was likely to increase further.

Lashkara claimed on the completion of its two years that Lashkara is at the first position among the Punjabi channels. A.G. Nelson was quoted as saying that Lashkar has 80 percent reach in Punjab and 50 percent in Delhi. (Lashkara Completes Two Era: Claims No.1 Punjabi Channel Status, 2001)

RTV Network ran into financial trouble long before the subscription plan was implemented and all channels had to shut down all channels for a few weeks in early 2002. 'Lashkara' which aired for a few weeks on 4 February 2002 (Reminiscent TV Network, 2009). After this it came to know that RTV The network is going to install new management after which Lashkara, Asia 1 TV. Sunali TV Will definitely be back soon. (Badhan, 2002)

Lashkara channel did quite well in the initial period, but later on it collapsed due to lack of finance and good content. In late 2004, a group of Non-Resident Indians (NRIs) represented by Riyaz Bhati bought the recession-hit Lashkara Punjabi's logo, software and brand channel promoters Subhash and Sunil Menon for Rs 4 crore. bought in (Singh, 2004)

ETC The network has two channels ETC Hindi and Adi ETC. Punjabi was started. ETC Network is a listed company of Bombay Stock Exchange. In the beginning, ETC The channel launched on 26 August 1999 with the punch line 'Phir Vi Dil Hai Hindustani'. It was a 24-hour channel with musical programs. The channel topped the music channels within 6 months and became the number one music channel in India. It was listed on the Bombay Stock Exchange in May 2000 (Srivastava, 2005).

ETC Punjabi and ETC Hindi channel run by 'Entertainment Television Network Limited'. 'Entertainment Television Network Private Limited' is a private company incorporated on 18 August 1998. It is classified as a non-government company and is registered with the Registrar of Companies in Mumbai. It manufactures television and radio transmitters and manufactures equipment for line telephone and line telegraph. (Entertainment Television Network Private Limited, 2020)

ETC Punjabi was launched in June 2000. It made the highest recognition in a very short time of three months. This channel was the first to take the right to broadcast Gurbani live from Sri Darbar Sahib for seven years. Currently, Zee Telefilm's ETC. had 51 percent shares. (Srivastava, 2005)

This channel was given permission by 'Ministry of Information and Broadcasting' on 5 February 2002 to do uplink and downlink through private satellite. This channel started from 7/B Shah Industrial Estate off Veera Desai Road, Andheri Mumbai. Along with this, the board directors of this channel were Jagjit Singh Kohli, Yogesh Radhakrishna and Yogesh Anandalal. (Singh, 2010)

In 2002, Zee Media ETC. took over Punjabi and then renamed it Alfa ETC, then ETC again. Punjabi and later Zee ETC. It came to be known as Punjabi Channel. Alpha Punjabi, (Zee Punjabi, Zee Punjab Haryana and Himachal) Presently known as Zee Punjab Haryana and Himachal, the channel started on 18 October 1999 as Alpha Punjabi Channel. (Essel Group, 2012) Alpha Punjabi channel used to broadcast information, entertainment and religious programs due to which this channel made its mark very quickly. Alpha TV Punjabi has continuously worked to provide the best Punjabi language content in all its forms. It was the only channel with the most diverse content portfolio such as news, programs on current issues, music, devotional programs, live chat shows, magazine shows, best Punjabi feature films, live programs etc.

In 2005, Alfa TV The name of Punjabi was changed to Zee Punjabi. The channel's status was changed to 'Hum Se Hai Shaan' in 2013. Due to the change of location of the channel, the channel was renamed Zee Punjab Haryana and Himachal to cater to the three states and the states of Punjab, Haryana and Himachal Pradesh. This channel broadcasts programs in Punjabi and Hindi languages. Covers news as well as current affairs. ("Zee Media Corporation Limited", 2015)

Zee Punjabi presented a fresh new look to kick off the 65th Independence Day celebrations. A new channel-packing especially changed its appearance. The change was visible from 00:00 am on 15th August and the channel tag line 'Apni Boli Apna Maan' a new tag line' and 'Khabr Vi Khyal Vi' tag line to keep Punjabis living in the world connected with Punjabi news. was given (Essel Group, 2012)

Continuing its commitment to instill a sense of pride in Punjabi culture, traditions and values in the hearts of Punjabis all over the world, Zee Punjabi Channel also focused itself more on news content. The channel had already gained a strong viewer base worldwide for its fair reporting and news coverage. Plans were being made to offer more news content to cement its image as a purely news channel in the future.

Zee Punjabi launched 'Himachal News' in Hindi on 2 May 2011. This bulletin used to be of 30 minutes duration. Zee Punjabi has been the pioneer in broadcasting news for another state on a Punjabi channel. Zee Punjabi editor Sanjay Vohra said, "This bulletin was long awaited by the audience in Himachal Pradesh as it will help them get a real picture of the state's situation in this hilly region and politically and socially. They will get strength. (Essel Group, 2011)

India's biggest live show 'Ek Omkar' Zee Punjabi enlightening the Punjabi audience about Sikhism and its true values was launched on June 1, 2010. The program used to last for two hours and was hosted by Gurpreet Singh, who played the lead role in the Punjabi film Baba Banda Singh Bahadur. Running daily between 5 am and 7 am, the show became very popular among Punjabi audiences worldwide and was praised by various religious groups and Sikh organizations. Giani Gurbachan Singh, Jathedar of Akal Takht Sahib, said that 'Ek Omkar' enlightened the audience on the correct perspective of Sikhism. Along with this, Jathedar appreciated the efforts of Zee Punjabi and said that this is the biggest devotional program that any channel has started, he congratulated the entire team of Zee Punjabi. (Essel Group, 2011)

'Zee Punjabi' has always thought of unique ways and colors to reach its audience. Zee Punjabi was rebranded as 'Zee Punjab Haryana Himachal' on 1 July 2013 at 8 pm, making it a 24-hour news channel. (Dung, 2013) Zee Media made Zee Punjabi a full-fledged news channel to strengthen its news cluster and aimed to increase regionalization and ensure a wide reach of the channel in Punjab, Haryana and Himachal Pradesh.

Conclusion

None of the channels except DD Punjabi has survived until now. Some of these channels succumbed to financial crisis. Alpha Punjabi TV was converted into news channel Zee Punjabi. One of the reasons for their closure is that these channels used to be run through private satellites which ran only on dish and cable but in those days the reach of dish and cable was very limited in rural areas. Due to which they could not reach the rural people.

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